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Effects of Multimedia Resources on Performance in Geography Concept among Secondary School Students in Saki, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the effect of multimedia resources on academic performance in geography among secondary school students in Saki West LGA of Oyo State. The study employed the experimental research design of the pre-test, post-test control group type. The population of the study comprised all the secondary school geography during the 2024/2025 academic session in Saki West Local Government area of Oyo State. The sample size consisted of 250 senior students (SSI- SSII) in 8 different schools selected from target population using stratified sampling technique. The instruments for data collection was Geography Performance Test (GPT). The instrument was self-constructed and content validated. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.70 using the split-half reliability test. The data were collected and analyzed using inferential statistics of the t-test type at 0.05 levels of significance. The findings of the study revealed that students performed better in geography when taught with the use of multimedia resources. The results further showed that male students outperformed the female students when taught with the use of multimedia resources. The study concludes that multimedia resources will improve the academic performance of students in geography in Saki West Local Government Area of Oyo State. The study recommends the use of multimedia resources in teaching geography in the schools and there should be provision for the devices by the stakeholders in the education industry to ease the teaching and learning process of the student.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Geography, Multimedia Resources.

Introduction

Assessment is an integral part in teaching processes that teacher used to determine the degree to which student have met the intended learning outcomes. It gives the instructor the confidence to know whether the teaching and learning has taken place or not. According to the Webster Dictionary (2017), assessment simply means appraisal. This is used to understand the state or condition of learning. Assessment refers to a related series of measures used to determine a complex attribute of an individual or group of individuals ((Tomás and Acquino 2018). Assessments are also used to identify individual student weaknesses and strengths so that educators can provide specialized academic support educational programming, or social services. In addition, assessments are developed by a wide

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array of groups and individuals, including teachers, district administrators, universities, private companies, state departments of education, and groups that include a combination of these individuals and institutions (Tomás and Acquino 2018)

It has been observed that traditional method of teaching and learning still exists with the level of multimedia's instructions available for teaching and learning in different part of the world. However, since the use of technology advancement has taken the streets of the world, people have sought to incorporate technology in their day-to-day lives. This is successful to the point that nearly every household has technological appliance (Cosmas and Kaiko, 2021). The use of multimedia in teaching is a mutual benefit for both the teachers and the learners; the teaching would be easy while delivering and the students tend to retain what they see and touch. Application of multimedia in teaching and learning brings a positive result on students' academic performance (Suresh and Patted, 2018).

Multimedia refers to any computer mediated software or interactive application that integrate text, colour, graphical images, animation, audio sound and full motion video in a simple application (Pavithra, Aathilingam and Prakash, 2019). Multimedia learning system offers a potentially venue for improving students understanding about the subject. Wang, Teng, and Chen (2015), Bouzid, Khenissi, Essalmi, and Jemni (2016) posits that multimedia technology in teaching and learning raises students learning interest, ability and confidence, and allows students to involve themselves in the subject matter and generation of ideas and think creatively. Beckers et al. (2016); Su and Cheng (2015), also reported that the use of recent technology-based learning environments enhances students to fully engaged in learning process and create competing motivations for task completion, along with their need for recognition and self-valuation.

Academic performance refers to the degree of a student's accomplishment in a task being given to them in studies in order to know how far and how well they comprehend the lesson. The most well-known indicator of measuring academic performance is grades which reflect the student's score for their subjects and overall tenure (Shehzad & Aziz, 2019). This can also be seen as the conceptualized academic performance as the knowledge gained by students which can be mainly assessed through the use of marks by the teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time (Narad and Abdullah, 2016). These objectives can be only achieved either using continuous assessment or examinations results. Academic performance is seen as the knowledge attained or skills, shown in the school subject.

Geography is a social subject in senior secondary school, and as a discipline course in tertiary institution of various part of the world which plays a vital role in human development. This is because it studied the human and its immediate environment. The planet which is embedded in geography happens to be the heart beat which nearly all human activities take place, and it is logical that man understands the nature and the character of the world, as well as the consequences of interactions between man and his environment (Urbanus and Alexander, 2021). (Aman, 2011) defined Geography as an interdisciplinary field of study that influences agriculture, industry, commerce, economic development. This simply implies Geography touches everywhere. (Schiller, 2012) also defined

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Geography as the study of places, persons, and the usual and established atmospheres they inhabit. It is the study of natural features and phenomena on the earth's surface and in the atmosphere. It also focuses on locations, space relations, and changes of physical phenomena on the earth's surface (Abdulkarim, 2010 & Aderogba, 2011).

It is observed that Geography is been taught in a way that discourages open questions, inquiry and active participation of the students (Sofowora and Egbedokun, 2010). The objectives of teaching geography at Senior Secondary Schools level were spelt out by National Policy on Education (NPE) of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) and reinforced by examination bodies namely, the West African Examination Council, (WAEC,2016) and National Examination Council, (NECO,2016) and curriculum development body such as Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008). These objectives have been thought of in terms of what geography can contribute to the realization of the aims of secondary education in Nigeria and include; giving students a sound knowledge of their immediate environment; inculcate in students' useful skills and outlooks that will enable them to make useful contribution to their community and nation at large; To develop in students the critical thinking ability, accuracy and objectivity for proper and logical investigation; among others (Aderogba, 2012).

Bunyi, (2013) considered the following Multimedia materials Scientific calculators, PCs, Mobile Phones, Weather focus devices, Televisions, Radios, Internet, Audio visual devices, Magnetic compasses as usually beneficial for the teaching of Geography. According to Amengor, (2011), Audio-visual tools like video, makes Geographical lessons look simple for learners and thus lessens the immaterial nature of the subject. Presentation software, 23 electronic atlas, Multimedia and replication programs are also essential technologies for Geography education (Bunyi, 2013). Power Point demonstrations for example can be ingeniously used to connect pictures, sound, movies and text to make Geographical proceedings brilliant. The usage of these technological resources when integrated with operational practical PCs skills, may add an entire new dimension to the education of Geography (Persaud, 2014).

According to the WAEC Chief Examiners' Report (2023), over 60% of candidates scored below Credit (C5) in geography, teachers' overemphasis on theory at the expense of practical geography, inadequate use of topographical maps and GIS tools in classrooms. NECO's 2023 Geography Report also echoed similar concerns about the performance of student in geography that many candidates could not sketch or label geographical features (e.g., drainage systems, weather instruments) correctly and their responses in answering questions lacked depth, critical analysis, and real-world examples. The responses from teachers and examiners (January–May 2024) attributed the poor result to rushed syllabus coverage post-COVID-19, increased malpractice cases (reliance on exam leaks) rather than genuine learning as well as lacking of geography labs in some school to aid teaching and learning. Inadequate coverage of syllabus has posed some serious effect such inadequate knowledge of the subject; poor presentation of answers; inability to draw good outline of maps of Nigeria, West Africa and Africa; inability to locate and name given features on map of Nigeria, West Africa and Africa; and the presentation of maps by the students are very poor and inability to use keys/legend to the features

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The study area for this research is Saki West LGA area Oyo State, Nigeria, with headquarter at Saki town. It is located between Latitudes 8° 40' 31" N and Longitude 3° 23' 38" E of the Greenwich Meridian Figure 3.1. It covers a total landmass of 2,014 km². Saki West L.G.A is located in the North Western part of Oyo State. It is bounded by two towns, Saki-East and Atisbo LGA. In the north eastern part, it is boarded by Saki-East and in the Southern part by Atisbo. In the North Western part, it shares a political boundary with Benin Republic and in the North Kwara State. Saki West LGA is subdivided into 11 wards: Ajegunle, Aganmu/Kooko, Bagii, EkokanMua, Iya, Ogidigboa/Kinnikinni, Oke-oro, Okere I, Okere II, Sangote/Baabo and Sepeteri/Bapon (Oyo State Ministry of Land Survey).

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design, specifically the pre-test, post-test control group approach, to assess the impact of multimedia resources on academic performance in Geography among secondary school students in Saki West Local Government Area (LGA) of Oyo State, Nigeria.

Population and Sampling

The target population comprised all Senior Secondary (SSI–SSII) Geography students in public schools across Saki West LGA during the 2024/2025 academic session. A stratified sampling technique was employed to select 250 students from 8 different schools, ensuring representation across gender and school types. The schools were randomly assigned to either the experimental group (taught with multimedia resources) or the control group (taught using conventional methods).

Research Instrument

The Geography Performance Test (GPT) was developed as the primary data collection tool. The instrument was self-constructed, content-validated by Geography education experts, and subjected to a pilot test to establish reliability. Using the split-half reliability method, a reliability coefficient of 0.70 was obtained, indicating acceptable consistency.

Presentation of Results

Testing Hypotheses

Two research hypotheses raised in this research work were tested and verified using inferential statistics and presented in Table 1 and Table 2. Computer Statistic Software SPSS was used in the analysis. All tests were verified at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

Ho: There is no significant difference between students taught with traditional method and students taught with multimedia resources

Table 1: Results of t-test analysis of performance scores of the subject in the Experimental and the control groups.

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Variable	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t-value	t-crit	p-value	decision
Experimental	125	38.92	6.4	123	7.45	2.01	0.0014	Sig
Control	125	21.23	3.2					

Author’s Analysis, 2024; Significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance

The above result depicts the t-value of the analysis which is 7.45, while the p -value is said to be 0.0014 at 123 degrees of freedom. Since the p -value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This simply implies that, there is a significant difference between students taught with traditional method and students taught with multimedia resources.

Ho: There is no significant difference between student taught with traditional method and multimedia resources based on gender

Table 2: Result of the t-test analysis of Performance Scores of the students based on Gender

Variable	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t-value	t-crit	p-value	p-Alpha	decision
Experimental: Male	60	28.01	7.2	123	6.3	1.0	0.003	0.05	Sig
Female	65	23.31	4.6						
Control: Male	60	29.40	5.3	123	5.2	1.1	0.02	0.05	Sig
Female	65	24.17	6.2						

Author’s Analysis, 2024; Significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance

The table above shows that in the experimental group, the t-value of 6.3 is obtained and the p-value observed is 0.003 at 123 degrees of freedom. Since the p-value is less than the alpha value, it shows that there is significant difference. A significant difference implies the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference between student taught with traditional method and multimedia resources based on gender is rejected.

Conclusion

The study assessed multimedia resources on academic performance in geography among senior secondary school students in Saki west local government area, Oyo State. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- i. Students taught with multimedia resources performed better than their counterparts taught with traditional method.
- ii. The performance of male student taught with multimedia resources is significantly different from the performance of their female counterparts. The male students performed better than the female students.

Recommendation

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- i. The use of Multimedia Resources in teaching geography in schools should be encouraged and there should be provision for the devices by the stake holders in the education industry such as Federal Ministry of Education, State Ministries of Education, NERDC among others.
- ii. There should be periodic seminars, workshops and training for the teachers on how to appropriately and effectively use multimedia device.
- iii. The Association of Nigerian Geographers (ANG) should rise and address the issue of persistent low academic achievement, interest and retention of geography students in senior secondary schools.
- iv. Stakeholders' in educational sector should implement policies that can help and encourage female students to learn using multimedia resources.

References

- Abdulkarim, B. (2010): The Perception of Geography as a Subject among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*. 5(1).99-103.
- Aderogba, K.A. (2012): Improving Teaching and Learning Aids in classes of Geography in Ogun state (Nigeria) Senior Secondary School (SSS). *International Journal of Research in Education*. Vol 3 (2), 250 – 255.
- Aman, S. (2011): What are the aims and objectives of teaching geography? <http://www.preservearticles.com>
- Amengor, J. (2011): History teachers' perception of I.C.T. in promoting teaching and learning. University of Cape Coast: Unpublished Dissertation.
- Bunyi, G. (2013): *International Journal of Education Development, Nairobi: University Press*.
- Coamos. C. & Kaiko M. (2021): The use of ICT in teaching of Geography in selected schools of Petauke district in eastern province of Zambia. *International Journal of Research and innovation in social science*. Vol. V, ISSN 2454-6186.
- Eze, E. (2021): Why Secondary School Geography Students Perform Poorly in External Examinations. University of Nigeria Nsuka. *Research Square Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-28665/v2>
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013): *National Policy on Education*; Abuja, Federal Ministry of Information.
- Narad, A. & Abdullah, B. (2016): Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students: Influence of Parental Encouragement and School Environment, *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 3(2), 12-19.
- National Examination Council (2023): *Regulations and Syllabuses for Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) for Candidates in Nigeria*. Minna.
- Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (2008): *Geography Curriculum for Senior Secondary Schools 1-3*. Federal Government Press, Lagos.
- Obudigha, W. (2010). Examination Malpractice in Nigerian Schools. Retrieved from: wisdom4ward.blogspot.com/.../examinationmalpractice-in-nigerian.htm

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- Pavithra, A., Aathilingam, M. & Murukanantha, S. (2019): Multimedia and its Implication. *International Journal for Research & Development in Technology*. Vol-10, Issue-5 (Nov-18) ISSN (O): 2349-3585
- Schiller, J. (2012): Interventions by school leaders in effective implementation of information and communications technology: Perceptions of Australian principals. *Journal of Information Technology for Teacher Education*, 11(3), 289–301.
- Shehzad, M. O. & Aziz, A. (2019): Achievement Goals and Academic Achievement: The Mediating Role of Learning Strategies, *Foundation University Journal of Psychology*, 3(1), 1-23
- Sofowora, O. A. & Egbedokun A. (2010): An Empirical Survey of Technology Application in Teaching Geography in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*. Vol.3 No.1 2010
- Suresh, K. & Patted L.B (2018): A Study of Relationship between Academic Achievement in Geography and Multimedia Approach among Secondary School Students. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, Vol 5, Issue 12
- The West African Examination Council (2023): Chief Examiner's Report, *Geography Paper 1*. Abuja, Federal Government press.
- Tomás and Acquino.Y. (2018): Assessment and Evaluation in Education 2018.
- Urbanus, B.T and Alexander R.B (2021): Effect of Multimedia on student performance in geography among senior secondary school students in Guyuk Local Government Area, Adamawa state, Nigeria. *IJARIE- ISSN (O)- 2395-4396*.
- Wikipedia:Link:<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multimedia>.